

SCHOOLFAN BEST PRACTICES:

AGAINST DISINFORMATION ABOUT CLIMATE CHANGE

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01

Executive Summary

Disinformation regarding climate change constitutes one of the most pressing social and educational challenges of the 21st century. The rapid spread of misleading content across digital platforms directly impairs scientific understanding and hinders informed decision-making, particularly among younger generations. In this context, this guide—developed under the framework of the European project SchoolFan—aims to provide practical tools, innovative methodologies, and educational resources to empower teachers, students, and the general public to identify, analyze, and counteract climate-related fake news.

Aligned with European Union priorities to promote responsible and informed citizenship, the project specifically contributes to improving climate change education in Portugal, Spain, France, and Greece (with all content also available in English). By fostering critical thinking and strengthening media literacy, the guide focuses on several interconnected key areas:

- **Media and Information Literacy:** Developing skills to verify sources and detect manipulated information.
- **Digital Competencies & Science Education:** Enhancing the capacity to contrast online myths with solid scientific evidence.
- **Civic Engagement and Citizen Science:** Promoting active, evidence-based participation in environmental policies and sustainable practices.

Ultimately, this document serves as an essential framework to transform classrooms into resilient spaces against environmental disinformation, ensuring public debate remains anchored in scientific truth.

PREFACE

Climate change communication takes place in a complex information environment. There is strong scientific consensus, but it coexists with fragmented narratives, emotionally driven content, and digitally generated or manipulated material. Social media platforms, algorithmic systems, and AI tools contribute to the large-scale spread of information, often with limited traceability of origin or accuracy.

The European Union has developed a regulatory framework to address these challenges. The Digital Services Act (DSA) strengthens platform responsibilities regarding content moderation and systemic risks linked to disinformation and algorithmic amplification. The Digital Markets Act (DMA) aims to ensure fairer and more transparent digital markets. The European Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) introduces a risk-based approach to AI regulation. It establishes requirements for transparency, safety, and human oversight. It also addresses generative AI systems, including obligations related to the identification of synthetic content such as deepfakes and the traceability of high-impact systems.

Overall, this framework reflects the EU's response to the rapid evolution of digital technologies and their societal impact. At the same time, it shows a clear challenge: regulation often moves more slowly than technological change.

The purpose of this guide is to support critical understanding of climate change disinformation and to strengthen the ability to interpret and evaluate information in an evolving digital environment.

However, as digital technologies evolve quickly, and artificial intelligence is accelerating how information is created, modified, and shared, what is considered reliable today may soon be outdated or disputed, especially when online circulation is faster than verification processes.

INTRODUCTION

01

1.1. Purpose of this Guide

Disinformation about climate change constitutes one of the main social and educational challenges of our time. The spread of misleading or false information directly affects scientific understanding, informed decision-making and civic engagement, particularly among younger generations. According to recent European Union data, 76% of young Europeans report having recently encountered disinformation online, highlighting the growing impact of digital misinformation on democratic participation and public understanding of global issues (European Parliament, 2025).

In a digital environment characterized by the rapid circulation of content through social media and digital platforms, citizens are increasingly exposed to inaccurate or manipulated information. At the same time, climate change remains a major concern among European citizens: 85% of Europeans consider climate change to be a serious problem, and 81% support the European Union's objective of achieving climate neutrality by 2050 (European Environment Agency, 2025). These figures demonstrate both the relevance of climate issues in public debate and the risks posed by disinformation to informed civic engagement.

Within this context, education systems play a fundamental role in promoting critical thinking and developing the skills necessary to identify, analyse and counteract disinformation. Strengthening media literacy and scientific literacy has therefore become an educational priority across Europe, particularly in relation to climate communication and digital citizenship.

This guide aims to provide practical tools and educational resources that help teachers, students and the general public better understand climate change disinformation and learn how to identify and verify misleading information.

1.2. The relevance of climate change and disinformation

Climate change is one of the most pressing global challenges of the 21st century. However, alongside scientific evidence, a large volume of misleading information circulates online, generating confusion and distrust toward scientific knowledge.

The spread of climate disinformation affects not only public debate but also citizens' ability to make informed decisions about environmental policies and sustainable practices. For this reason, strengthening media and information literacy is essential.

The SchoolFan project responds to European priorities related to:

- Media and information literacy
- Digital competencies
- Science education
- Civic participation

These priorities are aligned with the objectives of the European Union to combat disinformation and promote responsible and informed citizenship.

Through the development of educational resources, teacher training programmes and this best practices guide, the project contributes to improving climate change education in Portugal, Spain, France and Greece with content also available in English.

1.3. The SchoolFan Project:

What does it propose?

The SchoolFan project aimed to provide innovative educational tools and methodologies that enable teachers and students to better understand climate change disinformation and develop critical skills to address it.

The project focuses on several key areas:

Key concepts addressed in the project

- Disinformation and misinformation
- Climate-related fake news
- Media and information literacy
- Digital competencies
- Science education
- Civic engagement and citizen science

1.4. Development of educational resources

The project included the creation of pedagogical and digital materials designed to support teachers and students in identifying and analysing false or misleading information related to climate change.

1.5. Citizen science approach

One of the innovative aspects of SchoolFan was its implementation as a **citizen science project**. According to the European Citizen Science Association, citizen science is the participation of the public in science and research. It is an open and inclusive approach, with key characteristics including:

- 1) Citizens are actively involved in research.
- 2) There is a genuine science outcome, such as new scientific knowledge, conservation action or policy change.

In SchoolFan, students actively participated in information analysis, research and fact-checking processes.

Through this approach, students became active participants in the generation and verification of knowledge rather than passive consumers of information. The data generated by the students from their social media was then analysed by the SchoolFaN team and results reported in a publication as well as the final online dissemination meeting.

02

TARGET AUDIENCE

TARGET AUDIENCE

02

This guide is designed for a broad range of audiences interested in combating climate change disinformation.

2.1. Primary target groups

- Teachers in secondary education in the subjects of Biology, Geology, Physics, Chemistry, Geography, Language and Computer Science
- Students in secondary education in the subjects of Biology, Geology, Physics, Chemistry, Geography, and Computer Science
- Trainers of pre-service and in-service teachers for the subjects of Biology, Geology, Physics, Chemistry, Geography, Language and Computer Science

2.2. Secondary target groups

- Families and parents
- Media professionals
- Fact-checkers and communication experts
- Digital platforms (such as YouTube) and social media users

2.3. Institutional stakeholders

The guide may also be useful for organisations and institutions involved in education, media literacy and science communication, such as:

- Teacher associations
- Educational institutions
- Citizen Science community- e.g. European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)
- European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO)
- International Fact-Checking Network
- Educational policy decision makers

2.4. General public

Finally, this guide is intended for anyone interested in understanding how climate change disinformation works, how to identify it and how to train students to identify it.

03

UNDERSTANDING CLIMATE CHANGE DISINFORMATION

UNDERSTANDING CLIMATE CHANGE DISINFORMATION

03

3.1. Theoretical basis: Misinformation, disinformation and malinformation

The analysis of climate change disinformation should be situated within the broader framework of “information disorder”, a concept that better captures the complexity of the current information ecosystem than the politicized and reductive term fake news.

This framework encompasses a wide spectrum of problematic content, including misleading headlines, manipulated visuals, content shared out of context, impersonation, and entirely fabricated information (UNESCO, 2018).

Within this context, it is essential to distinguish between misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation, particularly in relation to climate change.

Misinformation refers to false or inaccurate information shared without the intent to deceive, such as the misinterpretation of scientific findings or confusion between short-term weather events and long-term climate trends.

Traditional Media create panic by spreading fake news and/or processed images [sic]

Disinformation, by contrast, involves the deliberate creation and dissemination of false information with the intention of misleading audiences, often through coordinated efforts aimed at denying anthropogenic climate change, amplifying uncertainty, or undermining scientific consensus.

Recycled products and electric vehicles are useless and dangerous [sic]

Malinformation, is based on factual content that is used out of context or strategically to cause harm, for instance by selectively presenting data to question climate policies or discredit key actors.

Although these categories differ in terms of intent, they often coexist and reinforce one another within broader communication strategies. Their combined effects include generating public confusion, eroding trust in science and journalism, and delaying effective climate action. Understanding these distinctions is therefore crucial for addressing climate change disinformation and fostering a more informed public debate (UNESCO, 2018, p. 46).

It is important to be aware of key terms related to misinformation. Below, we outline the most relevant ones.

- **False connection:** “When headlines, visuals or captions don’t support the content. The most common example of this type of content is clickbait headlines”. “This can also happen when visuals or captions are used, particularly on sites like Facebook, to give a certain impression, which is not backed up by the text”.
- **Misleading content:** “This type of content is when there is a misleading use of information to frame issues or individuals in certain ways by cropping photos or choosing quotes or statistics selectively”.
- **False content:** “One of the reasons the term ‘fake news’ is so unhelpful, is because genuine content is often seen being re-circulated out of its original context. For example, an image from Vietnam, captured in 2007, re-circulated seven years later, was shared under

the guise that it was a photograph from Nepal in the aftermath of the earthquake in 2015”.

- **Imposter content:** When genuine sources are impersonated. “There are real issues with journalists having their bylines used alongside articles they did not write, or organisations’ logos used in videos or images that they did not create”.
- **Manipulated content:** “Manipulated content is when genuine content is manipulated to deceive. An example from South Africa shows manipulated images of HuffPost Editor-at-Large Ferial Haffajee– in one case, sitting on the lap of a businessman, Johan Rupert – imputing a personal relationship with him”.
- **Fabricated content:** New content is 100% false, designed to deceive and do harm. This type of content can be text format, or it can be visual.

Manual Unesco 2018 (p. 48-50)

3.2 What is particular to climate change disinformation?

Within the framework of climate change disinformation, one particularly relevant practice is **greenwashing**, which refers to the dissemination of false or misleading information about the environmental benefits of a product, service, or policy (Lamb et al., 2020). Unlike other forms of disinformation, greenwashing does not necessarily involve denying climate change; rather, it operates more subtly by constructing an image of environmental responsibility that is not supported by actual practices.

This phenomenon is especially problematic because it can create a **false sense of progress**, diverting attention away from genuinely effective solutions and hindering accountability among companies and institutions. Moreover, the strategic use of “green” labels, advertising messages, and sustainability narratives helps shape positive perceptions among audiences, even when the real positive environmental impact is minimal or non-existent. In this way, greenwashing lies at the intersection of disinformation and persuasive communication, becoming a key element within the broader ecosystem of climate-related information disorder.

Examples of greenwashing

- **Misleading Labels:** A product may be labeled as “natural,” “eco-friendly,” or “organic” without any verification or certification. For instance, a cleaning product labeled “green” may still contain harmful chemicals.
- **False Claims about Recyclability:** Some companies may market their packaging as recyclable when only a small part actually is, or it requires specialized facilities unavailable to most consumers.
- **Offsets without Real Action:** Companies may claim to be carbon-neutral by buying carbon offsets instead of actually reducing their emissions.
- **Minimal “Eco-Friendly” Product Lines:** Brands might promote a single environmentally friendly product in their lineup as evidence of their “green” values, while the majority of their products are unsustainable.
- **Overstating Environmental Benefits:** A fashion brand might highlight sustainable materials, like recycled polyester, but not disclose that the production process involves harmful chemicals or unsustainable practices.
- **Renewable Energy Claims without Transitioning:** A company may advertise using “100% renewable energy” for operations but actually source only a fraction from renewables while purchasing certificates to make up the difference.
- **Vague or Irrelevant Claims:** Phrases like “eco-conscious” or “sustainable” are often used with no clear definition. For example, “non-toxic” labels on products that wouldn’t naturally contain toxins can mislead consumers.
- **Rebranding without Changing Practices:** Some companies might rebrand with green logos, earthy tones, and “natural” visuals without making any substantive environmental changes.

3.3. Identifying fake news related to climate change

Climate disinformation can take many forms, from completely fabricated information to misleading interpretations of scientific data.

Recognising this type of content requires critical analysis of sources, context and evidence.

3.4 Warning signs of misleading information

Some common indicators of disinformation include:

- Sensationalist headlines
- Lack of credible sources
- Manipulated images or videos
- Misinterpretation of scientific studies
- Content designed to provoke strong emotional reactions

Learning to identify these signs is a key step in combating the spread of false information.

04

**TEACHER
TRAINING
PROGRAMME
AND TOOLKITS
DEVELOPED IN
THE SCHOOLFAN
PROJECT**

TEACHER TRAINING PROGRAMME AND TOOLKITS DEVELOPED IN THE SCHOOLFAN PROJECT

04

SchoolFan provided a structured training programme designed to support the development of teachers' and students' skills competencies in media literacy, climate education and fact-checking. The training course developed within the project is available in four languages, making the resources accessible to a wider European audience. This toolkit provides materials, activities, and practical guidance designed to support teachers and students to identify, analyse, and critically evaluate information, while also promoting media literacy and critical thinking skills.

It is intended for use by both teachers, teacher trainers and students as a complementary resource to support the development of environmental awareness and information verification skills, and it can be adapted to different educational contexts.

It is recommended as a support tool when working on topics related to climate change and fake news.

The toolkits are available on our Zenodo community page

EN: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19202663>

FR: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19822804>

GR: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19882610>

ES: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19827050>

PT: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19859933>

The educational toolkit provides teachers with:

- 1) Training and evaluation materials and
- 2) Activities to implement these training sessions in the classroom with students:

1) Training materials for teachers

- **Training material on Climate Change:** An Introduction to the Fundamentals of Climate Change
- **Training materials on Climate Change and Fake News:** An Introduction to Information Disruption.
- Training materials on Citizen science in identifying and debunking fake news about climate change

2) Classroom activities for these sessions: Instructions for implementing the topics through classroom activities.

1. Climate/weather and climate change: verification of information: photographs, videos, and information sources.
2. Climate change and fake news: visual disinformation and emerging technologies: Artificial intelligence and generated images.
3. Climate change and fake news: identifying fake news on social media so that students can identify and classify it (TikTok and Instagram).

4.1 Verification to information

The first step is to consider how to recognize and identify reliable information and how to detect potential cases of misinformation.

Information verification can be done through photographs, videos, and sources provided by the news story.

Once you have identified information that may be false in any of the indicated formats (photos, video or sources), you need to ask yourself these questions, indicated below.

- Is the content creator known and does the post belong to a known news media?
- Is the url something you might expect by the content creator? Is it relevant to the title of the content creator?
- Is the information of the text complete and reliable? Do tables and references exist where is needed? Are the references reliable? Check the title.
- Check the underlying emotions. Is the news written the way expected by professional news media or reputable resources or is it aiming to provoke your emotions and cause fear?
- Does the content creator benefit economically or politically?
- Do I recognize the news organization that posted it?
- Does the information in the post seem believable?
- Is the post put according to the style that you would expect from a news organization?
- Could the post have political motivation?

(Sources: International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 2019; Kiely and Robertson, 2016; Lutzke, 2019; van der Linden, 2017).

4.1.1. How to verify photographs

Images are often used to support misleading narratives. Reverse image search tools can help determine whether an image has been taken out of context or manipulated.

How to verify photographs:

1. Reverse image search. It allows you to search for an image using data from another image, or to find where it has been published on the Internet. This option is useful when we have an image but do not know anything about the people or objects appearing in it. It is possible to find similar images that can give us a clue. TinEye (<https://www.tineye.com/>).
2. Metadata extraction. Both images and other types of files can contain metadata (data that describes the document), such as information about its author, content, format, or technical characteristics. In some cases, this metadata can provide useful information. VerExif (<https://www.verexif.com>).
3. Forensic analysis: it examines metadata but can also determine how an image may have been modified (whether it has been edited and certain pixels changed, whether it contains hidden pixels, etc.); it can also magnify parts of the image, analyse shadows (to detect any unusual details), etc. Forensic analysis requires some knowledge of image editing. FotoForensics: <https://fotoforensics.com>; Image Verification Assistant: <https://mever.itl.gr/forensics/>.

Other aspects that can be assessed:

- a) The source of the photograph. Whether or not it is reliable.
- b) The accompanying text. Many of the photographs used in disinformation campaigns are linked to misleading text or are used to take an event out of context (for example, through inaccuracies regarding the location of an event or discrepancies in the actual timeline).
- c) Determining the geolocation of a photograph is important. If the photo contains landmarks (buildings, mountains, signs), you can use other people's knowledge or an app to confirm whether the location matches what is claimed in the image.
- d) Check the information regarding nature in the photo: is the season the correct one? Are species the ones you would expect in that ecosystem?

Activity:

Detecting Manipulated or AI-Generated Images

Teachers are invited to try an activity designed to help them identify fake news in class with their students: How to verify photographs.

1. Identifying manipulated or fake images is becoming increasingly difficult. However, there are still some clues that can help us detect images created or altered by artificial intelligence.
2. In the following exercise, you will train your ability to detect fake or manipulated images. To do this, visit the following website: <https://detectfakes.kellogg.northwestern.edu/>
3. While completing the exercise, pay attention to the following details:

Face: Manipulations are often related to facial transformations.

- **Cheekbones and forehead:** Does the skin look too smooth or too wrinkled? Does the level of aging match across hair, eyes, and skin? Fake images may show inconsistencies.
- **Eyes and eyebrows:** Are there shadows where you would expect them? AI images may fail to represent natural physics.
- **Glasses:** Are reflections realistic? Do they change correctly with movement?
- **Facial hair, moles, or marks:** Do they look realistic? AI may add or remove these features unnaturally.
- **Blinking:** Does the person blink too little or too often?
- **Lip movements:** Do the lip movements look natural and synchronized?

Surroundings

- Do the surroundings look natural?
- Are shadows and lighting consistent?
- Do signs and text make sense?
- Do they match the location and season?

4. Record your results

Image	True/Fake?	Correct?	What clues helped you identify the manipulation? / What misled you?

4.1.2. How to verify videos

Videos can also be edited or presented in misleading ways. Analysing the original source, publication date and context is essential to assess their credibility.

How to verify videos:

1. Some institutions have developed free tools for analyzing videos. These include, among other features:

- a. the extraction of key frames—that is, images extracted from the video for more detailed analysis;
- b. the use of forensic techniques (similar to those used with still images, though somewhat more complex);
- c. the use of geolocation;
- d. the identification of metadata;
- e. the extraction of key frames, which allow for an alternative search for still images;
- f. other options. One of these is the Invid Project <https://www.invid-project.eu>.

Activity:

Content Analysis with Disinformation Elements

An activity called “Content Analysis with Disinformation Elements” is proposed. In this activity, students are shown different examples of disinformation in order to learn how to identify false content and understand its main components.

1. The materials include content related to the wildfires in Los Angeles (January 2025), especially videos and posts that claim these events are directly caused by climate change or global warming. Students are asked to analyse these videos carefully, paying attention to elements such as the source of the information, the images used, the emotional language, and whether there is any scientific evidence supporting the claims.
2. In addition, students are encouraged to verify the content using fact-checking tools and to reflect on whether the videos may be misleading, taken out of context, or manipulated.
3. Finally, a class debate is organised where students share their conclusions and discuss different points of view. This helps them develop critical thinking skills and become more aware of how disinformation spreads through video content on social media.

4.1.3. How to verify information sources

Identifying sources is essential for factchecking. To do this, we must compare multiple sources, consult scientific publications, and verify the credibility of authors and institutions. This way, we can determine whether the sources are reliable or not.

Other areas of analysis: geolocation, weather, chronological and archive network analysis.

This activity is provided: teachers are invited to try an activity designed to help them identify fake news in class with their students.

Activity:

How to distinguish news

1. Read the following post and take some time to answer the questions below:

Frances Swaggart
February 5, 2024

“Why is climate change or global warming a lie?” The climate, throughout history, has changed, that’s true. What we consider to be false is the political agenda behind “climate change,” which rides on the back of the propaganda machine generating fear in people by reporting increases of floods, droughts, heat waves, etc., and describing every one of them as “historic, extreme, and deadly”. the number of hurricanes, they tell us is on the rise, but the fact is, that numbers is down. they blame for all of course this they say. is us –humans have caused this – and the solution is to stop using fossil fuels. of course this doesn’t seem to apply to china, india, or politicians who travel by jet. thThey want us using electric cars, which we’ve seen too many of abandoned on roads. Here’s what we need to realize, folks, the politicization and lies about climate change —it’s a scam. It’s a scam to get the taxpayer’s dollar and control what types of cars U.S citizens drive, how our farmers grow our food, and what types of stoves American families can use to cook it —that is the purpose of all this climate change nonsense. As believers, let’s look to God and what he has to say about the climate. In his covenant with Noah. God said, “while the earth remaineth, seedtime and harvest, and cold and heat, and summer and winter and day and night shall not cease”. He’s not changing a thing.

Write a comment...

<https://acesse.one/eyyuiw1>

2. Think about it

- Does the source of the news seem reliable?
- Does the information in the news appear real and trustworthy?
- Check the logo (if any) and the website. Do they look real and credible? Why?
- Is the content creator an expert on the topic or do they cite real experts? Does the website or creator belong to a recognised news organisation?
- Is the URL or Facebook post what you would expect from the creator? Is it consistent with the title?
- Is the information complete and reliable? Are there data, tables or references where necessary? Are the references trustworthy?
- Check the underlying tone: Is the news written like professional journalism, or does it aim to trigger emotions and create fear?
- Does the creator benefit economically or politically from this content?
- Do you recognise the media outlet or the person who published it?
- Does the information in the post seem credible?
- Does the publication have the style of a reliable media source?
- Does it have a political agenda?

3. Discuss.

4.2. Visual disinformation and emerging technologies

4.2.1. Artificial intelligence and generated images

Recent technological developments allow the creation of highly realistic images and videos using artificial intelligence. These technologies can be used to manipulate public perception and spread misinformation.

Recent experimental studies show that AI-generated messages can be as persuasive as those written by humans. In some cases, they are even perceived as more factual and logical, especially when dealing with controversial or polarized issues (Bai et al., 2023).

Despite this, there are still several indicators that can help us detect deepfakes and AI-generated content (Bai et al., 2023; Kamali et al., 2024; Kaur et al., 2024; MIT Media Lab).

When analysing images or videos, one useful area to examine is the human face. For example, inconsistencies in facial expressions, unnatural movements, or irregular details in the eyes, teeth, or skin may indicate manipulation.

In addition, it is important to analyse the source of the content, check the context in which it appears, and use verification tools when possible. Developing critical thinking skills is essential to identify misleading or false content and to prevent the spread of misinformation in digital environments.

AI systems often struggle to perfectly replicate certain natural features. For example:

The process of detecting fake news consists of a series of steps to identify its reliability. Below are the processes used by data verifiers.

- **Eyes:** AI may produce unnatural or inconsistent pupils, sometimes with irregular or jagged edges instead of smooth circular shapes.
- **Facial details:** Small inconsistencies may appear in skin texture, lighting, or symmetry.
- **Limitations:** AI-generated content may appear increasingly sophisticated and realistic, making inconsistencies, manipulation, or false elements more difficult to identify.

With the rise of AI-generated content and images, it is advisable to take two steps:

1) Morphological Anomalies

1. Pay attention to the face. High-end DeepFake manipulations are almost always facial transformations.
2. Pay attention to the cheeks and forehead. Does the skin appear too smooth or too wrinkly? Is the agedness of the skin similar to the agedness of the hair and eyes? DeepFakes may be incongruent on some dimensions.
3. Pay attention to the eyes and eyebrows. Do shadows appear in places that you would expect? DeepFakes may fail to fully represent the natural physics of a scene.
4. Pay attention to the glasses. Is there any glare? Is there too much glare? Does the angle of the glare change when the person moves? Once again, DeepFakes may fail to fully represent the natural physics of lighting.
5. Pay attention to the facial hair or lack thereof. Does this facial hair look real? DeepFakes might add or remove a mustache, sideburns, or beard. But, DeepFakes may fail to make facial hair transformations fully natural.
6. Pay attention to facial moles. Does the mole look real?
7. Pay attention to blinking. Does the person blink enough or too much?
8. Pay attention to the lip movements. Some deepfakes are based on lip syncing. Do the lip movements look natural?

2) AI filters:

various tools can be used to provide a statistical probability of whether an image or text was generated by AI models. There are a number of free apps available, but it is advisable to check their reliability first.

4.2.2. Detecting manipulated content

Understanding how these technologies work helps users identify manipulated or artificially generated content.

Detecting Manipulated Content: Step-by-Step Process

1. Data collection (Dataset)

The process begins with the collection of a dataset that includes fake news, rumours, and information about users and their relationships in social networks. This helps to understand how manipulated information spreads.

2. Data preprocessing and annotation

The data is cleaned, organised, and labelled to make it suitable for analysis. This step ensures that the dataset is structured and reliable for further processing.

3. Model selection and propagation graph construction

A diffusion model is selected, and a propagation graph is created. This graph represents how information spreads across different users and networks.

4. Feature selection and temporal analysis

Relevant features are identified, and the temporal evolution of the content is analysed. This includes when the content was published and how it changes over time.

5. Source reliability evaluation

Different metrics are used to assess the credibility of information sources. This helps distinguish between trustworthy and suspicious sources.

6. Source pattern analysis

The system examines whether the content is supported by a single source or multiple sources, which is important for detecting potential manipulation.

7. Validation of results

Finally, the results are validated to determine whether the content is manipulated, misleading, or false.

Conclusion

Overall, this process demonstrates how data analysis and computational models can be used to detect manipulated content and reduce the spread of misinformation.

4.3. Example of climate disinformation from the SchoolFan Citizen science project

4.3.1. Classroom implementation and examples

This section presents real examples of climate disinformation circulating on digital platforms.

Activity:

Classroom implementation of the SchoolFan Citizen Science project as an educational activity

Target public:

Students over 14 years old, Biology, Geology, Physics, Chemistry, Geography, Computer Science, Foreign or native language education History.

The following consists of our suggestions on how secondary education teachers could implement SchoolFaN as an educational activity in order to train their students to identify and debunk fake news about climate change, and at the same time becoming familiar with citizen science projects.

Instructions for teachers:

1. Familiarize yourself with the SchoolFaN educational materials (see the links in the toolkit). You can use the proposed materials or any others you deem appropriate based on your own research.
2. Teach students how to recognize climate change misinformation (you can use the activities described above).
3. If you use mobile devices or laptops in the classroom, you can implement this activity or assign it as homework outside of class.
4. If you can conduct this activity in the classroom: Ask students to log into their TikTok, YouTube, and Instagram accounts, search for specific hashtags (e.g., #climatechange, #drought, #fires, #floods), and evaluate the posts/videos they find as either true or false. You can choose the duration that best suits your class. For example, students could conduct the search for a week or more. If they find posts/videos

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containing false news, you can ask them to complete the activity in the classroom. We suggest printing it out as a reference material for them to review before starting and to discuss any questions in class.

5. When the students finish, you can:

- a. Compile all the reported false news and discuss it in class, for example, why it is considered false.
- b. Check fact-checking websites to see if the posts you identified as false have also been identified.
- c. If not, your class can contact a fact-checker and report the results. (The material mentioned above is available in English, Greek, French, Portuguese, and Spanish at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20020606>).

4.3.2. Why are these examples misleading?

This example is considered false or misleading because it uses inaccurate claims, decontextualised images, or unreliable sources to support the message. Verification processes show that the content does not match reliable scientific evidence or trusted information sources.

Each case is analysed to explain the strategies used to distort information and how fact-checking processes reveal the inaccuracies.

Example 1:

Fact checking and fact checkers

The photograph on the right (1) is a screenshot taken from a video linked to the widespread flooding caused by the DANA (Isolated High-Level Depression) between 29 and 30 October 2024. However, it actually shows flooding that took place in Zaragoza (Spain) in July 2023. And the photo on the left (2) is real and verified.

Example 2:

Fact checking and fact checkers

Various types of disinformation can be observed: fake photos and images linked to the 2025 Los Angeles wildfires, as well as erroneous political attributions that link these wildfires to the SmartLA 2028 institutional plan. Furthermore, false claims have been attributed to NASA, which contradict the need to reduce polluting emissions and deny their influence on climate change.

Example 3: Social Media

The claim that “there have always been hot summers” is a fallacy based on false equivalence and oversimplification. It confuses “weather” (the heat on a single day) with “climate” (the long-term global trend). Furthermore, it ignores the fact that the current problem is not the heat itself, but its unprecedented intensity, frequency and extent.

4.4. Steps to help you identify fake news (teachers)

The training program of the “Anti-Fake News Agency” Academy is designed to provide agents (teachers) with the necessary knowledge to deal with the spread of fake news.

“The truth will come to light” during the training, which is structured in four stages:

1. Learn from experts

Students study articles written by professional fact-checkers. They try to understand their methodology and argumentation (debunking). Learners are given a “real” case of fake news related to climate issues, along with an analysis produced by fact-checkers.

2. Act like experts

This stage includes two steps:

- **Know your enemy:** Students take part in the online game “Bad News”. They enter a simulated social media environment and take on the role of creators of fake news (pre-bunking).
- **Find your enemy:** Students are asked to identify possible fake news on the internet and verify the facts (pre-bunking and debunking – inoculation). If possible, they also try to trace the original source of the misinformation and identify its weaknesses and motivations.

3. Learn as experts

Students are encouraged to deepen their knowledge of a topic such as climate change, where misinformation is common and socially relevant. They are provided with scientific articles and websites from international organizations and official media outlets.

4. Teach non-experts

Learners are required to train their own “assets” (students) in the same way, so that the AFNA program has a real social impact.

How to Deal with Fake News?

1) Fake news related to climate change, such as:

1. Climate change does not exist
2. Climate change is not caused by humans
3. Climate action is useless
4. There is plenty of climate action

2) Identifying fake news related to climate change based on:

5. Reliability of sources
6. Journalist’s name and position
7. Quality of references
8. Quality/type of URL

05

**CLASSROOM
IMPLEMENTATION
AND RESOURCES
FOR TEACHERS**

CLASSROOM IMPLEMENTATION AND RESOURCES FOR TEACHERS

05

5.1 Learning from classroom experiences

Teachers can integrate media literacy and climate change education into different subjects through a cross-curricular and competency-based approach. In the SchoolFan project, the toolkit supported this integration into regular teaching practice, allowing teachers to adapt activities to their specific school contexts, subjects, and student profiles.

The implementation across countries faced several challenges, mainly related to school organisation, policy restrictions, extreme climatic events and difficulties in collecting data in different educational settings. In some cases, these limitations reduced full classroom implementation and required activities to be moved to homework or adapted to school constraints. Clear differences were observed between countries in how the project was applied.

In Spain, implementation focused on the collaborative development of educational materials and their use in a flexible way across different subjects and classroom contexts. In France, teachers made strong and immediate use of the toolkit after training, implementing activities in class and promoting student collaboration. The citizen science component was usually introduced after the main lessons, although in some cases it was adapted due to exam periods and partially assigned as homework.

In Portugal, teachers designed or adapted lesson plans based on student needs, ensuring the integration of climate change, disinformation, and citizen science as core elements. Students were actively involved in producing outputs and raising awareness within their school communities, and in several cases interdisciplinary collaboration strengthened the implementation.

In Greece, teachers showed high engagement and used the toolkit consistently. However, national restrictions on mobile phone use limited in-class access to social media, meaning that part of the citizen science activity had to be completed as homework, except in Computer Science lessons where computer labs could be used.

This reduced the in-class participation in some cases. Overall, implementation was based on three main principles: cross-curricular integration, collaborative adaptation of materials, and a combination of classroom and out-of-class activities.

The approach contributed to the development of key competencies such as media literacy, critical thinking, digital competence, and environmental awareness. Methodologies were practical, contextualised, problem-based, and interdisciplinary, supporting a deeper understanding of scientific and social issues. Overall, the project strengthened students' ability to analyse information critically and engage with complex environmental and societal challenges.

Table 1. Integration of activities into the school curriculum

Element	Description
Overall approach	Cross-curricular integration of media literacy and climate change education using a flexible toolkit
Main implementation model	Adaptation to school contexts, combining classroom work and homework when needed
Main challenges	School organisation, policy restrictions, and limited access to digital tools in some countries
Subjects involved	Biology and Geology, Physics and Chemistry, Citizenship Education, Computer Science, History and Geography
Key topics	Climate change, misinformation, ecosystems, digital environments
Competencies developed	Media literacy, critical thinking, digital competence, environmental awareness
Methodologies	Practical, contextualised, problem-based, and interdisciplinary learning, citizen science, project based learning as many students produced products such as campaigns, courses, videos, websites, games etc.
Key outcome	Improved students' ability to critically analyse information and understand complex environmental and social issues

5.2 The role of teachers in the project

In the project, teachers play a central role as facilitators of learning, guiding students in the critical analysis of information, the verification of digital content, and the understanding of climate change and disinformation. Their main function is to support the learning process, providing guidance, structure, and tools that enable students to actively engage in research and learning activities.

Across all participating countries, teachers begin by introducing key concepts such as climate change, fake news, and citizen science in order to establish a shared understanding among students (see link to resources). From this point, their role shifts towards a more practical and supportive function, where students take an active role through tasks such as analysing real digital content, classifying information, and producing their own materials.

Teachers support students in selecting and analysing digital sources, including images, videos, and social media content, helping them develop skills in verification and critical thinking. They also encourage discussion and reflection on digital information, raising awareness of the

impact of misinformation on society and the environment.

Although the overall approach is shared, implementation differed depending on national contexts. In Spain and France, activities were mainly carried out in the classroom with direct teacher support, promoting collaborative work. In Portugal, teachers took a more structured facilitative role, designing learning pathways and new citizen science proposes that often lead to student-produced outputs. In this case they also acted as role models, facilitators and motivational agents, supporting students through the project, products and events production process. In Greece, due to regulatory restrictions, a significant part of the activity is completed as homework, reinforcing the teacher’s role as a guide beyond the classroom but limiting the possibility of a detailed guidance.

In some cases, teachers also act as coordinators, sharing materials with colleagues and promoting the integration of the project across different subjects. Overall, their role was defined by flexibility, adaptation, and continuous support, ensuring that students remain at the centre of the learning process while developing critical, digital, and scientific competences.

Table 2. The role of teachers in the project

Element	Description
Main role of teachers	Act as facilitators of learning, guiding students in critical analysis, fact-checking, and understanding climate change and disinformation
Common pedagogical approach	Introduction of key concepts (climate change, fake news, citizen science) followed by student-centred practical activities
Classroom function	Continuous support, guidance in selecting and analysing digital content (social media, images, videos), and fostering critical thinking

Methodologies used	Active learning, real-case analysis, digital content evaluation, discussion, and student-generated outputs
Competences developed	Critical thinking, media literacy, digital literacy, and environmental awareness
Extended role of teachers	In some cases, coordination with other teachers and dissemination of the project within schools
Key idea	Teachers guide and support; students actively investigate, analyse, and construct knowledge

5.3 Data collection and understanding of the scientific process

Through citizen science activities, students learn how scientific knowledge is produced, tested, and validated in real contexts. This process helps them understand not only scientific content, but also how evidence is gathered and interpreted in relation to complex issues such as climate change and misinformation.

Across all countries, students engaged in data collection activities linked to real-world problems, particularly climate change and its causes and consequences. They were introduced to key elements of the scientific method, including hypothesis formulation, data collection, evidence analysis, and the distinction between scientific knowledge and personal opinion. In doing so, they also developed an understanding of the role citizens can play in contributing to scientific research and knowledge production.

In Spain, the process was structured around hands-on citizen science activities that helped students understand how scientific knowledge is generated and validated. Students co-

llected and analysed data related to climate change and were encouraged to interpret evidence critically. However, it was observed that some students understood the practical tasks more easily than the broader concept of citizen science itself, suggesting the need for clearer pedagogical guidance and stronger in-class support. It was also recommended to prioritise classroom-based implementation, including the analysis of social media content, to strengthen engagement and understanding.

In France, citizen science activities helped students better understand climate change by working with real examples and evidence. The approach increased motivation, as students felt they were learning through direct discovery rather than evaluation or grading. Teachers noted that the concrete nature of the activity supported engagement and understanding. However, they also suggested that more time should be dedicated to fake news analysis and climate-related activities to deepen learning outcomes.

In Portugal, student engagement varied depending on prior knowledge and familiarity with citizen science. Some students had never encountered the concept, while others had pre-

vious experience. Motivation increased when students realised they were contributing to real data collection, particularly within their own digital environments. The use of mobile phones in class also acted as a strong motivating factor in contexts where this is usually restricted. However, time allocated for misinformation analysis was often considered insufficient, leading teachers to adapt the activities or extend them as homework. In some cases, additional citizen science initiatives were developed, such as analysing urban heat islands, and students were actively involved in designing research plans, collecting data, and presenting results.

In Greece, neither teachers nor students were initially familiar with citizen science. Through participation in the project, they developed an understanding of its principles and recognised its potential for active involvement in scientific research. Students also became aware of

fact-checking tools and practices they had not previously encountered. Although engagement was high, teachers highlighted that completing most activities at home reduced their impact, and they considered classroom implementation more effective. In some cases, students presented their results through posters and school events, increasing visibility within the school community.

Overall, the implementation showed that citizen science helps students understand how science works in practice, while also developing critical thinking and analytical skills.

Key feedback across countries was also highlighted the importance of clear guidance, sufficient time, and strong integration into classroom practice to maximise its educational impact.

Element	Description
General approach	Students learn the scientific process through citizen science linked to real-world issues (climate change and misinformation)
Core skills developed	Hypothesis formulation, data collection, evidence analysis, and distinction between opinion and scientific knowledge
Main challenges	Limited time, homework-based implementation, and difficulty fully understanding the broader concept of citizen science
Best practices	Hands-on data collection, real-world contexts, student-led research, and classroom-based implementation
Key outcome	Improved understanding of how science is produced and validated, and development of critical and analytical thinking skills

06

IMPLEMENTATION AS A CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECT

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06

SchoolFan was designed and implemented as a citizen science project. More than 350 students from Spain, France, Portugal and Greece and 93 teachers participated in the activity. Given that one of the objectives of the SchoolFan project was to assess students' ability to identify climate-related fake news on social media, an activity was carried out in each of the participating countries (Portugal, France, Greece and Spain).

As indicated in the “classroom implementation and examples” section (4.3.1), a citizen science activity was proposed in which students were asked to indicate both the number of climate-related posts containing fake news that they had found and the total number of posts they had seen during their search. These data were used to calculate a perceived prevalence of climate-related fake news for each participating country. The key results are:

1. The fake news related to climate that students found in the social media (Instagram, TikTok, YouTube) in all participating countries.
2. The differences existing between platforms in relation to the results.
3. The students' evaluation regarding the findings obtained as: true, false, misleading or uncertain.

1) The fake news related to climate that students found in all participating countries.

The results suggest that students found climate-related fake news in all participating countries, although with substantial differences between national contexts:

Figure 1. Overall perceived prevalence of fake news across social media platforms.

Portugal showed the highest perceived prevalence, with approximately 27% of the posts analysed by students identified as containing fake news. Spain and Greece presented similar values, with perceived prevalence rates of 20% and 19%, respectively. France showed the lowest perceived prevalence, with approximately 8% of posts identified as containing fake news.

These results should be interpreted with caution. They do not represent the objective prevalence of climate-related fake news in each country or on each platform. Rather, they reflect what students found, recognised and reported during a structured educational activity. Therefore, the findings are better understood as an indicator of students' **exposure to and perception of climate misinformation in specific digital search contexts.**

2) The differences existing between platforms in relation to the results.

The analysis by platform also showed relevant differences among the participating countries:

Figure 2. The differences of perceived prevalence of fake news between social media platforms.

In Spain, the perceived prevalence was highest on TikTok (26%), followed by YouTube (22%) and Instagram (15%). In France, the perceived prevalence was comparatively low across all platforms, ranging from 7% on Instagram to 10% on TikTok. In Greece, TikTok again presented the highest perceived prevalence (26%), while YouTube showed the lowest value (13%). In Portugal, the highest perceived prevalence was observed on Instagram (30%), followed by TikTok (22%) and YouTube (20%).

Taken together, these results indicate that climate-related misinformation is not confined to a single platform. Different social media environments may expose students to different levels and forms of problematic content. This reinforces the need for educational activities that do not focus exclusively on one platform, but

instead help students transfer critical evaluation skills across different digital contexts.

3) The students' evaluation of the credibility of their findings as:

true, false, misleading or uncertain. Students evaluated the credibility of climate-related content found online. Students were asked to indicate whether they considered each post to be true, false, misleading or uncertain on social media. The results show substantial differences between the participating countries. It is worth noting that after fact checking 20% of students' entries, the students produced reliable categorisations (between 80 and 90% correct, which is considered to be a reliable outcome in citizen science studies).

Do you think the post is true?

Figure 3. Assessment of Truthfulness, Misinformation, and Uncertainty in Climate-Related Online Content by Students

Portugal showed a high proportion of posts perceived as false or partially false (54.3%), followed by 25.2% perceived as true and 15.0% as partially true but misleading. Greece showed a more distributed pattern: 30.3% of posts were perceived as true, 27.6% as partially true but misleading, 23.7% as false or partially false and 18.4% as uncertain. In France, the majority of posts were perceived as false or partially false (69.0%), while only 9.0% were considered completely true. In contrast, in Spain, the largest proportion of posts was perceived as completely true (40.0%), while 28.9% were classified as false or partially false and 22.2% as partially true but misleading.

These differences suggest that students did not encounter or interpret climate-related content in the same way across countries. In some contexts, particularly France and Portugal, students more frequently identified content as false. In others, such as Spain and Greece, a larger proportion of posts was perceived as true or ambiguous. This reinforces the importance of teaching students not only to identify obviously false claims, but also to recognise more subtle

forms of misinformation, including misleading framing, partial truths, emotional language and decontextualised information.

From a best-practice perspective, these findings support the importance of combining climate education with media and digital literacy. By involving students in the identification and analysis of climate-related fake news, SchoolFan fosters an opportunity for students to critically reflect on their own information environments. This is central to the SchoolFan objective of strengthening students' digital, scientific and citizenship competences, while supporting teachers with scalable strategies to address climate misinformation in the classroom. It should be noted that the results were conditioned by algorithms, searches, language and students' digital habits. Therefore,

they reflect the perceived exposure to climate misinformation and not the real amount existing on the internet. The differences between countries and platforms do not mean that there is more misinformation in some places than in others. Students' media competences and critical capacity also may have influenced the

results. Although many students detected suspicious content, verification practices were limited. This demonstrates the importance of reinforcing media, digital and scientific literacy skills, hence the importance of indicating the most relevant results so that this activity can be replicated in any country, taking these points into account:

1. Students need scientific knowledge about climate change and practical strategies to evaluate how climate-related information is presented online. The activities encourage students to: 1) compare information across platforms, 2) examine the credibility of sources, 3) distinguish between evidence-based information and misleading claims, 4) practise verification strategies such as checking original sources, consulting reliable scientific institutions and 5) using fact-checking resources.
2. The differences between countries and platforms also suggest that educational interventions should be adaptable. Teachers may benefit from using examples taken from the platforms most familiar to their students, while also encouraging them to explore how the same climate topic may be represented differently across TikTok, Instagram and YouTube. This platform-sensitive approach can help students recognise that misinformation is not only a matter of false content, but also of context, format, source credibility, emotional framing and algorithmic visibility. By involving students in the identification and analysis of climate-related fake news, SchoolFan fosters an opportunity for students to critically reflect on their own information environments. This is central to the SchoolFan objective of strengthening students' digital, scientific and citizenship competences while supporting teachers with scalable strategies to address climate misinformation in the classroom.

3. The issue of climate misinformation should go beyond simple true/false classification exercises. Students should receive support to explain why a post may be misleading, how it can be verified and which sources are appropriate for checking climate-related claims. This includes developing practical verification skills to check the reliability of information. Such activities include tracing information back to original sources, comparing claims across reliable media outlets, identifying the origin and possible manipulation of images or videos, consulting scientific institutions and using dedicated fact-checking platforms when appropriate.

The SchoolFan group understands that this type of classroom-based citizen science approach is useful. It captures how students navigate real digital environments, reveals differences in recognition and verification practices, and provides teachers with concrete entry points to strengthen climate, media and digital literacy.

07

LESSONS LEARNED

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The main lessons learned throughout the development of the project are related to the challenges identified, the impact achieved, the adoption of implemented solutions, and the recommendations proposed for future actions.

Below is a summary presented in two tables that systematically outlines the most relevant findings drawn from the project’s experience for two distinct audiences: teachers and trainers, on the one hand, and researchers on other stakeholders.

Table 3. Main lessons learned and future recommendations for teachers and trainers.

Teachers and trainers				
	Area / Challenge	Impact	Adopted solution	(Future) recommendation
1.	Teacher recruitment and training	Uneven participation and engagement across schools	Align activities with curriculum priorities and offer recognition (e.g. media visibility, credits or certification) and support during the implementation phase	Provide institutional incentives, support throughout implementation and formal recognition for teacher participation and visibility to their work
2.	Teachers trained but unable to implement	Lack of implementation in some schools. in some cases due to bureaucratic issues in collecting data.	Engage head teachers and school leadership early	Formalise institutional agreements to ensure implementation
3.	Students found tasks difficult	Reduced learning effectiveness	Provide scaffolding and teacher guidance	Simplify tasks and improve instructional clarity

4.	Time constraints	Limited classroom time	Integrate activities into existing lessons	Modularise and shorten activities
5.	Digital technologies not allowed in school	Restricted use of on-line platforms	Use homework or exemptions	Establish clear digital-use protocols
6.	Climate change events in real time	Difficulty linking to current events	Use available real-time examples	Develop updated dynamic resources
7.	Teachers/trainers only reporting cases with fake news	Limited dataset and bias in reporting	Encourage systematic reporting regardless of findings	Standardise reporting templates to ensure consistency

Table 4. Main lessons learned and future recommendations for researchers and other stakeholders

Researchers and other stakeholders				
	Area / Challenge	Impact	Adopted solution	(Future) recommendation
1.	General implementation constraints	Incomplete or partial implementation in some contexts	Flexible adaptation to each school context and calendar	Strengthen coordination with schools and support to ensure minimum implementation standards
2.	Low response rate (homework-based)	Reduced participation	Combine classroom and homework formats	Prioritise in-class data collection
3.	Ethical / GDPR concerns	Hesitation in collecting or using student-generated data	Apply strict anonymisation and clear ethical guidelines	Develop standardised GDPR-compliant protocols for all partners
4.	Teachers reporting only fake news cases	Biased dataset	Encourage systematic reporting	Standardise reporting templates
5.	Informed consent (student participation)	Exclusion of some students	Provide alternative classroom tasks	Ensure inclusive participation models
6.	Sustainability of the CS project	Lack of long-term continuity	Collaborate with fact-checkers and organisations	Build long-term institutional partnerships

08

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

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08

The SchoolFan project has demonstrated that education can play a key role in tackling climate-related disinformation, particularly when students are actively involved in processes of analysis, verification, and knowledge-building. However, its results should not be seen as an endpoint, but rather as the beginning of a broader and evolving educational process. In an increasingly complex digital environment—shaped by rapid technological change, the expansion of social media, and the growing influence of artificial intelligence—the challenges linked to disinformation continue to intensify, requiring adaptive and forward-looking responses.

Against this backdrop, the lessons learned through SchoolFan highlight not only the value of media and information literacy, but also the need to continue strengthening educational strategies that empower young people to critically engage with information and navigate emerging digital realities. The recommendations presented below build on these insights and seek to contribute to the ongoing discussion about how education can respond to the opportunities and challenges posed by the AI era. Rather than definitive solutions, they are intended as guiding principles for fostering informed, resilient, and responsible digital citizens in a rapidly changing world.

The following are our recommendations and the main challenges of artificial intelligence.

A) Recommendations (future)

Teachers & Teacher Trainers

1. Early planning and curriculum alignment

It is recommended to develop mapping tools that link project activities with national curricula before implementation, ensuring stronger pedagogical coherence.

2. Integration into school planning

The project timeline should be integrated into schools' annual planning from the outset, facilitating organisation and implementation.

3. Coordination with schools

Stronger coordination with schools is necessary to ensure minimum implementation standards and a more consistent application of the project.

4. Modularisation of activities and adaptable models

Activities' duration should be reduced or structured into smaller modular units to improve flexibility. Also, share editable and adaptable resources.

5. Inclusive participation models

Inclusive participation models should ensure that no student is excluded due to technical, linguistic, or contextual barriers.

6. Support for teachers and recognition for their work

It is recommended to provide institutional incentives, support throughout classroom

implementation, and formal recognition for teacher participation that impacts their careers, as public visibility and recognition of the importance/quality of their work through social and mass media publications as a key factor to ensure long-term engagement.

7. Simplification of activity design

Task design should be simplified and instructions made clearer to support easier implementation in schools.

8. Updated and relevant resources

It is recommended to develop dynamic resources that are regularly updated in line with current climate events, ensuring relevance and educational value.

9. Long-term collaborations

Long-term partnerships should be established with institutions working on disinformation to strengthen impact and sustainability.

5. Cross-country harmonisation

Stronger harmonisation tools should be developed between partner countries to ensure consistent implementation at European level.

6. Data protection (GDPR)

Standardised protocols compliant with GDPR should be developed for all project partners.

7. Simplification of evaluation

Evaluation requirements should be reduced and simplified to minimise administrative burden and facilitate implementation.

8. Support for teachers and recognition for their work

It is recommended to provide institutional incentives, support throughout classroom implementation, and formal recognition for teacher participation that impacts their careers, as public visibility and recognition of the importance/quality of their work through social and mass media publications as a key factor to ensure long-term engagement.

Researchers and other stakeholders:

1. Classroom-based data collection

Whenever possible, data collection should be prioritised in the classroom, improving data quality and student engagement.

2. Standardisation of reporting

Reporting templates should be standardised to ensure coherence, comparability, and easier analysis of results.

3. Harmonised consent procedures

Consent procedures should be standardised across all countries to ensure legal and organisational coherence.

4. Long-term collaborations

Long-term partnerships should be established with institutions working on disinformation to strengthen impact and sustainability.

B) AI: The challenge

The challenge of artificial intelligence

Generative artificial intelligence should be a key future priority. AI's ability to produce highly realistic text, images, and videos creates new forms of disinformation. Education must respond by equipping students with the skills to identify AI-generated content, apply critical thinking to synthetic media, and understand the basic principles of these technologies, in order to strengthen resilience against emerging digital disinformation.

09

REFERENCE

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